

ACADEMIC INTEGRITY AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN STUDYING

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Abstract: *Academic integrity is one of the most pressing issues being studied in the field of science, and this article discusses the causes of plagiarism and the situations that arise as a result.*

Key words: *academic integrity, academic dishonesty, plagiarism*

Academic dishonesty is any form of academic conduct that is deceptive, dishonest, or fraudulent. Academic dishonesty includes deception, plagiarism, and forgery.

Deception includes the following points, among others:

- Using resources not authorized by the instructor (textbooks, notes, websites, other students' work) to complete exams or other assignments
- Giving or receiving substantive information related to assignments/quizzes/tests/exams to/from others unless authorized by the instructor
- Use of unauthorized electronic devices
- Submit academic work previously submitted in another course or by someone else.

Plagiarism is the intentional or unintentional use of the intellectual creations of another source, person, or organization without proper attribution. Any direct quotation, paraphrase, or summary of a work (in whole or in part) in one's own words, and any information not generally known, must be acknowledged. Plagiarism usually takes two main forms:

- Passing off someone else's ideas or words, images or other creative works as your own; and
- Using or relying on someone else's work without acknowledging the source, even when minimal information is available to identify it for citation.

Falsification is defined here as intentionally falsifying or fabricating any information or quotation.

"Fictitious" information (e.g., measurement results) may not be used in a laboratory experiment or academic work. The actual source from which the cited information originates must be stated.

Students may not modify or resubmit previous academic work without prior approval from the instructor.

Examples of academic dishonesty include, among others

- copying during a test or allowing another student to copy during a test;
- give another student homework, term papers, or other academic work to plagiarize;
- submitting work that is not your own;
- modifying a graded work and submitting the work for re-grading without the knowledge/approval of the instructor;
- theft or improper procurement of tests or other items of assessment;
- providing false or misleading information to the instructor in an effort to obtain a postponement or extension of a test or other assignment;
- unauthorized access to someone else's computerized records or systems;

Unauthorized recording, reproduction, forwarding, or redistribution of course materials (e.g., lectures, handouts, podcasts, exams, student projects, group work, online materials, etc.); and

- providing any material or information to another person with the knowledge that such assistance could be used in any of the above violations.

Why do people commit plagiarism?

- Hope for more success
- Time management
- For the sake of simplicity
- lack of competence
- Fear of bad grades
- Environment (peer pressure)
- Denial of responsibility

Consequences:

- Problems with teachers
- Destruction of own reputation
- Demotivation of fellow students
- Referral from university
- Failing exams
- Disapprovals
- bad notes
- you don't learn anything from it.

It's not worth taking the risk if you don't learn anything from it in the end.

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